

41217 OMAA Abu Dhabi Inter Arprt

SLAT 24.43
 SLON 54.65
 SELV 27.00
 SHOW 4.30
 LIFT 1.99
 LFTV 1.30
 SWET 54.20
 KINX 21.50
 CTOT 6.90
 VTOT 34.90
 TOTL 41.80
 CAPE 0.00
 CAPV 0.00
 CINS 0.00
 CINV 0.00
 EQLV -9999
 EQTV -9999
 LFCT -9999
 LFCV -9999
 BRCH 0.00
 BRCV 0.00
 LCLT 277.3
 LCLP 650.5
 LCLE 338.8
 MLTH 313.6
 MLMR 8.10
 THCK 5875.
 PWAT 23.33

00Z 06 Sep 2018

University of Wyoming

41217 OMAA Abu Dhabi Inter Arprt

SLAT 24.43
SLON 54.65
SELV 27.00
SHOW 3.08
LIFT 2.36
LFTV 1.73
SWET 70.21
KINX 25.70
CTOT 8.10
VTOT 36.10
TOTL 44.20
CAPE 0.00
CAPV 0.00
CINS 0.00
CINV 0.00
EQLV -9999
EQTV -9999
LFCT -9999
LFCV -9999
BRCH 0.00
BRCV 0.00
LCLT 272.0
LCLP 581.0
LCLE 337.5
MLTH 317.7
MLMR 6.16
THCK 5896.
PWAT 23.90

12Z 06 Sep 2018

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